

TYPES OF WORDS ACCORDING TO THEIR FORM AND RELATIONSHIP (IN THE EXAMPLE OF A WORK OF ART)

¹Atamurodova Qunduz G'aniyevna

Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy, teacher,

²Uralova Aziza Dilmurod qizi

Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy,

³Ubaydulla Shohista Hidoyatillo qizi

Termiz agrotexnologiyalar va innovatsion rivojlanish instituti, talaba.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481040>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2022

Accepted: 23th December 2022

Online: 24th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Homonym, synonym, antonym, lexeme, word forms, word variants, lexical layer, paronym, synonym series, phraseological synonymy, syntactic synonymy.

Words in a language vary in form and meaning. Some words are similar in form, some in meaning, and some in pronunciation. According to these characteristics, words are divided into the following groups:

1) homonym 2) synonym 3) antonym 4) paronym.

Applying these elements to a work of art is a testament to the writer's skill. And it makes the work serious. The use of these words, which are an integral part of language, depends on the individuality of each artist.

Normurad Norkobilov's novel "Blackbird" uses a lot of homonyms, synonyms and antonyms. The proper use of synonyms enhances the effectiveness and comprehensibility of the work. In fact, synonyms are important lexical units that reflect the individual characteristics of a writer's use of words. The place of synonyms in the process of artistic

ABSTRACT

There are many ways to organize the imagery of a literary text. As you know, the language of fiction is endless. Synonyms, homonyms, and antonyms are used effectively in the process of creating an artistic image, just as words that are specific to all forms of common lexical layers are used effectively in the process of creating an artistic image. In the use of word variants, as well as in the use of various word forms and expressions, it is possible to observe a general situation peculiar to the language of the work of art

discourse is determined by the expression of the concept at different levels. Because words in a synonymous series can express the meaning of a concept at different levels, depending on their emotional color.

It is these features that allow the idea to be expressed in a colorful way in a work of art. The abundance of synonyms used in the work of art testifies to the richness of the language of the work. After all, synonyms differ from other words in that they do not represent the same concept, but represent different states of the same concept. Therefore, the more diverse the synonyms in a play, the more attractive the language of the play. Purposeful use of synonyms allows the writer to express the idea accurately and expressively, preventing repetition of words that can be boring.

If we look at the lexical meaning of the word synonym, it is derived from a Greek word meaning "one name". The phenomenon of linguistic units having the

same meaning is called synonymy. Depending on the specifics of the language, the phenomenon can be divided into lexical synonyms, phraseological synonyms, and syntactic synonyms.

It is important to use more synonyms in the works. Synonyms cover all aspects of our lives. In this regard, Ferdinand de Saussure states: "The whole mechanism of language is only a resemblance and revolves around differences." Below we will try to interpret the synonyms from the novel "Blackbird" with real examples.

And if he is not immediately relieved of the burden of sleep, which hangs like a stone on his eyelids, soon this nameless creature will scatter the grass and smash the hives and needles.

The lexeme of being free is more commonly used in the artistic style and less commonly used in the oral, formal, and journalistic styles. Creates a synonymous line with words like get rid of, get rid of, get rid of. The dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language also mentions the addition of the word to the list of synonyms: to be free, to be free, to be free, to be free, to be free. The author prefers to choose an artistic synonym from this series.

We can also observe a series of synonyms in the play: If a dog like a blackbird is released, it will usually be the first wolf they seek in the endless mountains and rocks.

The words endless, infinite, infinite, that is, endless, are synonymous with the lexeme in the context. The creator used infinite and boundless synonyms side by side in the synonymous line, creating a small synonym line within the context. This is just a layer of his individuality. Synonyms have been used to enhance the art of the work to such an extent that only the features of the

artistic style have been deliberately chosen. Among the lexemes such as enemy, fat, enemy, rival, he prefers to use the lexeme of the enemy: Dogs will not be seen by enemies due to the dense spruce and grass. This also influenced the expressiveness of the work.

He shook his head sadly, thinking that he would rot among the stones, and said, "Put it in the well." In the explanatory dictionary of Uzbek synonyms, *im qoqmoq* means to call, to call means to call with gestures. A writer who uses synonyms skillfully is not afraid to use a dialectal lexeme from a synonymous series. On the contrary, it provides a variety of works:

"Now, my enemy's strength is coming from there!" The rough surface of the cave, which covered the path of the rock, looked like a plague to a man who had come out of the abyss of winter. The sudden appearance of the Armenian in the village posed a very difficult problem for Akbota. Now, don't get me wrong, just sit there.

Being ready is synonymous with the words to be careful, to be attentive, and is used mainly in dialect, more precisely in the Samarkand region; It can be synonymous with words like tiredness, exhaustion, exhaustion. The difference is that it is used in dialect; Suddenly, the lexeme is also a dialectal word and is synonymous with lexemes such as sudden, sudden, sudden, and the phrase "falling from the roof"; Sit still — this word is synonymous with the word sit still. But the fact that the first lexeme is a dialectal word is due to the speech of the protagonist Akbota. Because Akbota is a member of the tribe, the use of dialectal words in revealing the psyche of the tribe is a great help in reviving that environment.

In order to express the situation more vividly in the play, synonyms are used step by step: when the Armenian escaped from captivity, or more precisely, from the scourge of slavery, he kept his word - did not interfere in the river, did not join the wolf. The synonyms of captivity and slavery, as well as the synonyms of el and kur, served to express each other more clearly.

However, it was not because of any riots, but on a calm and quiet day that he was put on a sack in Chohlidara, not far from the valley, and taken to the uninhabited mountain tower of the mountain.

As mentioned above, Normurad Norkobilov first chose to use the words of artistic style in his work. The reason is that the word vaj, which is one of the synonyms of excuses, is a word of artistic style. The situation before the enslavement of the protagonist Erman could not be summed up in one word, so the synonyms of peace and quiet are used side by side.

One of the important features of synonyms is that the exact words that correspond to the purpose of the image are among these lexical units. The use of appropriate synonyms can vividly reflect the clarity of the image, the spirit of the protagonists, as well as the level at which the person is referring to others. For example, in the novel:

If we look at the context, we can see that the thoughts that Elder Akbota imagined belonged to his relatives were also the lexemes of conversation, conversation, and conversation. Is selected. Because the word is more specific to the way you speak. The writer sometimes puts two synonyms side by side from synonyms. In this case, the meaning of one word is

loaded on two words, which enhances the aesthetic effect:

This Armenian, who had endured all the pains and sufferings of slavery, was not like his predecessor. If only the word pain were used in this context, the reader would not have noticed that it was painful. One of the main problems in the study of the language of fiction is the artistic influence, the means of speech that play an important role in the formation of imagery, the disclosure of their laws. Because the means of language do not become the main material of the work of art, but in the process of development of the artistic language, it expands qualitatively and acquires subtleties of meaning.

He knows that there is no one in the village who is not afraid of evil. As the writer chooses each word, he avoids rudeness by choosing the lowest color of the negative word, just as he chooses the reader. The synonym duoyi bad lexeme avoids the use of the word curse because it does not want the second word to have the opposite effect. While the language of the work of art appears as an example of word art, it is based on the diversity of means of speech, the different meanings of words, as well as the diversity of levels of expression of the word. .

Although the Armenian was very kind by nature, he turned his back on his brother, who was very stingy with animals, especially in the field of horses and dogs. When the word jealous is used instead of the lexeme of greed in this sentence, the meaning that the lexeme should have expressed would be greatly diminished. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the highest level of lexemes in the synonymous series.

For the negative characters in the play, the creator does the right thing by choosing a word with a negative connotation in the synonymous line: Karakul is happy with his condition and works ugly. Smiling, laughing, grinning, laughing, sneezing — this synonymous phrase sneezes is a word with a negative connotation. For Karakul, who plays the main character in the play, the word with a negative connotation is skillfully chosen. Conversely, for the positive protagonist Omontoy, three synonyms are used instead of two to reinforce the meaning of the word:

Omontoy, like his fellow villagers, does not know how to hold a grudge, and concepts such as cake and enmity are completely foreign to him.

It was supposed to reveal that the protagonist had no feelings of anger, enmity, or resentment, and it was masterfully revealed. As a result of such expressive means of artistic expression, the artistic color of the work of art is enhanced and its aesthetic impact is ensured.

In addition to synonyms, the appropriate use of antonyms enhances the art of the work. Normurad Norkobilov was able to show his individuality in this regard. Before analyzing the antonyms in the work, let's look at the lexical side of the term. Two or more linguistic units took part in the synonym series, because they name and represent the same reality. In the case of antonyms, two linguistic units are involved, because such a relationship occurs between linguistic units that name and represent the opposite reality.

The main criterion for defining antonyms is the lexical meaning, that is, the fact that the words have opposite meanings, and the principle of logical center should be used to

determine whether the words are antonyms. Antonyms are one of the means of speech that provides a variety of speech that plays an important role in literary texts. Below we analyze the antonyms in the work using real examples.

As soon as you step over the rocky cliffs, you will immediately notice the smell of the cave, which does not fade in winter and summer.

It is a pair of winter and summer words and means "always". It is based on lexemes with opposite meanings. The use of contradictory lexemes enhances the color and aesthetic effect of a particular word in a work. The spirit of the work is similar.

Peace is not the result of the avalanches, which are constantly pouring in during the day, or the indiscriminate behavior of teddy bears, sometimes alone or in groups, and the bloody aggression of wolves, which are very active at night. .

In the above context, the words singular and plural are contradictory lexemes. These antonyms are used to describe a situation. These two antonyms are considered to be lexemes that retain the property of contradiction both inside and outside the context. Phrases also form a series of antonyms, but their use in the play is inextricably linked to the artist's skill.

You look like you're lying dead, you look like you're jumping in the air, you look like ...

The combination of a dead stretch and a blue jump phrase only creates an antonym in the context, and if we take it out of context, they don't create an antonym. Only with the skill of a writer did they come into play as antonymous units.

We can observe this situation not only in compounds, but also in lexemes:

In such cases, the parties do not feel animosity towards each other, and friendship ...

When we take enmity and friendship out of context, the antonym disappears. A writer who is able to elevate the art of his work makes it an antonymous lexeme in the context. The more contradictory words are used in the play, the more vivid and expressive the situation and the situation to be expressed.

Homonyms are another element of a writer's work of art, a testament to his eloquence. It is well-known that homonyms are words that have the same spelling and pronunciation, but different meanings. Because of this they are also called figurative words. In the novel "Blackbird" homonyms are used effectively and appropriately. This further increases the value of the work. Here are some of the ones I found to be interesting:

Of course, you can't smell it ...

Used in the sense of feeling in context. Wedding II— grinding, powdering. This lexeme creates a homonym within a word group.

Then the boy's attention is drawn to nothing but a red rock piercing the rock in front of the rock.

In the explanatory dictionary of Uzbek homonyms, the lexeme blue is interpreted as follows: blue I (quality) - air color, blue, blue; blue II (horse) - a layer of air in the form of a dome on the ground, the sky, the firmament, the sky; blue III (horse) - cilantro, dill, parsley, vegetable; blue IV (horse) is a large stitch. The word homonym is synonymous with the word heaven.

If the Armenian people had invaded and invaded his land, they would have been ambushed and killed.

In the above context, mulberry I (horse) is a leaf used to mean the fruit of a tree that feeds on silkworms. The suffix is a different set of words, related to the verb, meaning "to catch";

In general, this profession, which Kalaybek is engaged in, is a completely foreign profession for the people.

In this sentence, the word yat, which forms the form, occurs within different word groups: one belongs to the verb and the other to the adjective. In the play, it is synonymous with the word alien;

Therefore, it was difficult for Erman, who had been dismounted from his horse, to take a step at first. . It is the form of the verb that means "union." The fact that the Creator is able to use the omens in their proper place is also a testament to his skill;

Karakul's blackness fades, and soon a stone like a skull in his hand appears in the hole again.

The word stone is used in the context of stone — a solid body, carrying out the formation within the nouns and verbs;

"It blinds ..."

Blind I (quality) - the organ of vision is dysfunctional, deprived of vision; blind II (verb) - to see something. In the sentence, the word is used as the first syllable;

But before Karakul could reach the destination, he broke his promise, thinking that it would be spilled on the road.

In the explanatory dictionary of Uzbek homonyms, hair I (horse) is a hair on the human head; hair II (horse) - hair, snout; hair III (verb) - means to divide into parts. At the same time, in the context, the word is used in its third form, as a word in the verb category.

It should be noted that there are many ways to organize the imagery of a literary text. As you know, the language of fiction is endless. Synonyms, homonyms, and antonyms are used effectively in the process of creating an artistic image, just as words that are specific to all forms of common lexical layers are used effectively in the process of creating an artistic image. In the use of word variants, as well as in the

use of various word forms and expressions, it is possible to observe a general situation peculiar to the language of the work of art. There is no form of speech in which folk proverbs and wise sayings are as widely used as in the language of fiction and perform a methodological function. This free use of language is also an important feature of the language of fiction.

References:

1. Hojiyev A. O'zbek tili sinonimlarining izohli lug'ati. Toshkent. 1974
2. Norqobilov N. Qoraqyun. . O'zbekiston. 2016
3. Hojiyev A. O'zbek tili sinonimlarining izohli lug'ati. O'qituvchi. T:1974
4. Raxmatullayev Sh, Mamatov N, Shukurov R. O'zbek tili antonimlarining izohli lug'ati. Toshkent. 1989
5. Rahmatullayev Sh. O'zbek tili ommonimlarining izohli lug'ati. O'qituvchi. T: 1984